

THE ADVANTAGES OF MULTIMEDIA LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

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Modern world of emerging trends in technology, everything is flexible, especially the teaching of English language. Methods of teaching English language have developed rapidly over the past forty years. So it is important that language learners as well as teachers adopt and understand the various techniques of language teaching and upgrade themselves of the same. Teachers teaching English at various grades must also be able to adapt themselves to the needs of the young minds and how in turn will help to bring about drastic changes in the society. According to academic research, linguists have demonstrated that there is not one single best method to teach English language and that no one teaching method is inherently superior to the others. In this modern era of information and technology, due to rise in Globalization and Commercialization, English language teaching has become an integral part of our educational scenario and occupies a pivotal position. ICT has become an essential part in our daily life because technology has brought in several changes. In the recent years English language teaching has undergone drastic changes with the advent of latest methodologies and techniques .As language teachers it is important to understand and adopt the various methods and techniques and also apply them in classrooms. Language teachers should keep themselves abreast of the current trends to create inquisitiveness among the pupil community and prepare them for the challenges of the future. In this paper we focus on choosing the modern techniques and activities that are appropriate for each particular task, context and learner with a focus on motivation and helping learners become independent and inspired to learn more. It also throws light on how technology can be used in English classes to make learning more interesting and fun for pupils. Use of technology in English language

teaching In this age of Information and Technology, the use of Internet has brought many changes in teaching English. It is a highly useful tool which benefits both the learner and the teacher using it for many activities related to teaching and learning. Modern technology is developing at a faster pace, the learners and teachers have to upgrade The authors of the above-mentioned report list the following benefits of using multimedia environments for teaching and learning:

Multimedia can enhance learning in different locations and institutions of diverse quality; present opportunities to pupils working at different rates and levels; provide (tirelessly, without holding up other pupils) repetition when repetition is warranted to reinforce skills and learning; and compensate, in the short term, for high pupil populations and limited numbers of trained and experienced teachers – in combination with robust teacher development initiatives and improvements in teachers’ working conditions.

Updates to content ware can ensure that teachers and pupils encounter and have the chance to work with current and authentic sources. Such encounters tie learning to the most important events of our time and underscore the general idea that knowledge itself is not fixed and finalized, that there is a universe of discoveries and a library of analyses that can be available to pupils.”

There is little to add to this in general terms, but it is worthwhile considering the particular advantages afforded to FLT/FLL by the new media. The most popular and most widely used devices appropriated by modern language teachers remain the CD player and the audiocassette recorder. More recently, the Web has served as an additional source of authentic listening materials thanks to the possibility of fast downloads using MP3 software. The use of moving images linked to sound provides learners with exposure to all important elements of spoken communication: gestures, proxemics, pronunciation, intonation, all embedded in natural, cultural contexts. And devices like DVD players, videocassettes, web sources, the laserdisc and video cameras readily supply these. Thanks to modern technology, scenes can be located, isolated and replayed at random and there is an abundance of literature suggesting how to exploit film/video sequences meaningfully. Different forms of visual support

can now be offered (e.g. optional sub-titles in the mother tongue or target language to assist understanding and facilitate access to the language).

Both satellite and terrestrial radio and television programmes offer cheap access to contemporary, authentic, and potentially culturally rich programmes for the language learner. The immediacy of current affairs programmes ensures that learners' exposure to the language is up-to-date and embedded in the real world of native speakers. Linked to modern recording equipment, broadcast radio and television also offer the advantages of the audio and video devices mentioned above. A number of broadcasting companies still produce broadcasts, which are at their most effective when combined with face-to-face courses in educational institutions. It has gone a long way to overcoming the problem of the relatively poor quality of analogue transmissions, which has so far prevented this medium from being widely used for language teaching. Audio exchanges via the Internet now also provide possibilities for real time synchronous oral communication. The principal uses of the telephone to date have been limited to supplementary tutoring for those engaged in distance education. However, with the advent of digital quality and lower connection costs, there is now considerable potential for its extended use – including the possibility of conference calls.

Finally, with the introduction of the multimedia computer, the learner and teacher have at their disposal an instrument, which can combine all the advantages of the above-mentioned media in a compact and easily accessible form. The computer may be used as a local machine or within a network.

The list of used literature:

1. Byrne, Don. Teaching Writing Skills. - Longman Group UK Limited, 1988.
2. Emig, J. Writing as a Mode of Learning // College Composition and Communication, 1977. - 28 (2).
3. Evans, V. Successful Writing. Intermediate Student's Book. - Express Publishing, 2000.